

WORKBOOK

POSITIONALITY STATEMENTS TO OPEN UP YOUR RESEARCH

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Workshop Overview

Open Research encompasses a variety of practices for enhancing the accessibility, trustworthiness, and transparency of scientific research, such as pre-registration, sharing research materials and data, citizen science, open access publishing and more. To date, less attention has been paid to **“opening” research processes**, which increases the transparency of the researchers’ methodological decisions and choices and illuminates potential biases or hidden assumptions.

Reflexivity practices constitute one set of resources, traditionally used by qualitative researchers to examine researchers’ beliefs and worldviews and how these may influence research processes. Qualitative research is typically characterised by methodological approaches that embrace flexibility and subjectivity. It encompasses its own processes and procedures to ensure rigour, one of which is writing clear and coherent positionality statements.

This workshop, aimed at both qualitative and quantitative researchers, will introduce you to reflexivity practices and support you to draft **a positionality statement**, as a tool for reflecting on how your personal characteristics, experiences, and opinions could influence the research processes.

This workbook guides you through the process of designing a positionality statement, via a series of **interactive scaffolding exercises**. You will first be prompted to jot down your assumptions associated with your research. Then, you will receive support for and feedback on translating those into a draft positionality statement.

For the exercises in this workbook, we will follow several writing prompts to help us reflect. To get the most out of the exercises, follow these few instructions:

- a) Time your writing (we suggest a time with each prompt)
- b) Use -if possible- pen and paper or an empty digital notesheet, do **not erase** anything you wrote down
- c) Continue writing during the exercise, do not worry if you cannot finish a thought, leave it open and use a new line if that happens.

The exercises in this workbook are inspired by Annette Markham's. You can find more techniques on her blog:

<https://annettemarkham.com/2017/02/reflexivity-for-interpretive-researchers/>

Exercise 1: Uncovering hidden meanings, values, and assumptions

What does openness in research mean to you? Why is it important? (2 minutes 30 seconds)

The Iterative Inquiry Spiral (from Markham, 2017)

The process of uncovering one's assumptions about a topic resembles travelling down a spiral in order to repeatedly examine ideas, beliefs and thoughts to identify where they come from and what lies behind them.

Exercise 2: Uncovering your hidden assumptions about your research

2A. What are your assumptions about [fill in with your research topic]? How did they evolve over the time you spent researching this topic? (5 minutes)

Alternative Prompt: What would make for good qualitative open science? (5 minutes)

2B. What are your values, beliefs, and backgrounds? How might or could these values, beliefs, and background affect or shape your research into [fill in with your research topic]? (4 minutes)

A blank Social Identity Map as introduced by Jacobson and Mustafa in [1].

2C. What are the different assumptions and perspectives of your research team members on [fill in with your research topic]? To what extent are they similar or different to yours? How do you deal with that? (3 minutes)

Draft your own Positionality Statement

Please draft your own positionality statement here, reflecting on your role and identity in relation to the context and setting of the research (e.g., were you an insider or outsider, etc.), what was the relation with the research subjects, and what specific assumptions do you bring based on your research paradigm? (5 minutes for a first draft, but take as long as necessary to complete the statement)

Reflect about yourself

What are your assumptions about your research topic?

Which research paradigms are you using?

Other discussion prompts:

- How much detail should be included in a positionality statement?
- What else can you do to enhance the transparency of your research processes?
- How does this relate to Open Science and reproducibility?

Resources

1. Jacobson, D., & Mustafa, N. (2019). Social Identity Map: A Reflexivity Tool for Practicing Explicit Positionality in Critical Qualitative Research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 18, 1609406919870075. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406919870075>
2. Jamieson, M. K., Govaart, G. H., & Pownall, M. (2023). Reflexivity in quantitative research: A rationale and beginner's guide. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 17(4), e12735. <https://doi.org/10.1111/spc3.12735>
3. Academic Wheel of Privilege: MetaArXiv Preprints [Bridging Neurodiversity and Open Scholarship: How Shared Values Can Guide Best Practices for Research Integrity, Social Justice, and Principled Education](#)
4. See also the slides of a similar workshop: <https://osf.io/e5t36/>
5. Discussion about objectivity and bias in quantitative research: <https://cnsyoung.com/is-science-objective/>
6. More ideas for exercises:
<https://compass.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/action/downloadSupplement?doi=10.1111%2Fspc3.12735&file=spc312735-sup-0002-suppl-data.docx>
7. Markham, A. (2017). Reflexivity: Some techniques for interpretive researchers. <https://annetmarkham.com/2017/02/reflexivity-for-interpretive-researchers/>
8. Field, S., & Pownall, M. (2025). *Subjectivity is a Feature, not a Flaw: A Call to Unsilence the Human Element in Science*. OSF. https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ga5fb_v1
9. Cole, N. L., Ulpts, S., Bochynska, A., Kormann, E., Good, M., Leitner, B., & Ross-Hellauer, T. (2024). *Reproducibility and replicability of qualitative research: An integrative review of concepts, barriers and enablers*. <https://files.osf.io/v1/resources/n5zkw/providers/osfstorage/676406419eef7a6511e4b1c3?action=download&direct&version=1>

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